

1 **HPV infection results in induction of genomic instability.**

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6 HPV infection likely results in millions of deaths each year. We measured total transcription in the primary
7 keratinocyte following infection with HPV16 *in vitro*. We report here activation of *Recq14* at 7 days
8 post-infection with high-risk human papillomavirus type 16. The helicase induction either reflects a
9 genome maintenance effort or a repair activity associated with abortive integration-type activity rather than
10 non-specific repair or damage during viral infection.

11 Citations

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